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Crimes Act 1914 (Cth) – Part VIIC – Division 3: Sections 85ZV, 85ZW and Associated Definitions

Potential Interpretative Issues and their Impact

By Dr Jeffrey Barnes

Independent research report commissioned by the Australian Criminal
Intelligence Commission (NCIS Pilot Program)

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Acronyms

AIA	<i>Acts Interpretation Act 1901 (Cth)</i>
CbD	Compliance by Design
CtD	Compliance through Design
D2D CRC	Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre

Executive Summary

This report is an examination of central provisions of the spent convictions scheme in the *Crimes Act 1914* (Cth): ss 85ZV and 85ZW and associated definitions.

The main purposes of the report are four-fold: first, to ascertain what interpretative *issues* may arise; second, to determine what *types* of interpretative issues may arise; third, to indicate the *causes* of the interpretative issues; and fourth, to gauge the extent to which the issues can be *factored into* a legislative mapping exercise.

In this report ‘interpretative issues’ is broadly understood as capturing readings of a provision that require interpretative knowledge beyond a literal reading. It includes the classic interpretative issue where rival contentions as to meaning — called here ‘constructions’ — may arise. Some of these ‘issues’ may be weak or tenuous. It also includes the application of the law where that application involves a value judgement and requires taking into account the context of the provision. And it includes ‘readings’ of the provision where that reading is informed by legal knowledge of a relevant provision of an Act of general application, such as the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). The application of a provision of an Act of general application may produce a reading that is different to what a lay person would arrive at uninformed by such knowledge.

The spent conviction scheme in the *Crimes Act* appears to be well drafted. However, no legislative scheme is immune from potential interpretative issues, and the spent convictions scheme is no exception. Importantly, it is a misconception to see the potentiality for interpretative issues as necessarily evidence of a drafting mistake or a bad thing.

In summary, 19 potential interpretative ‘issues’ in the central provisions of the spent convictions scheme are identified. The issues are of three types. For convenience, they are labelled categories A, B and C. These categories are now briefly described.

Category A. The potential for issues in this category to arise is deliberately created. The potential is a by-product of the drafter using a style of drafting known as general principles drafting. Issues in this category can be readily identified to an extent.

Category B. The potential for issues in this category to arise may not be deliberately created. What has brought about the issues is not entirely clear and to an extent may be indeterminate. Moreover, the very existence of the issue itself is not settled. From the author’s perspective, the potential for the issue to arise is often uncertain and in many cases may be remote. And even if the facts arise to generate the issue, the argument for one side may be weak. In other words, the ‘issue’ may be tenuous.

Category C. The potential for issues in this category can be readily identified. The potential arises because of a potential difference of views amongst interpreters. The provisions concerned are not ambiguous to the well-informed interpreter, but they require that person to apply specialist interpretative knowledge not

ordinarily possessed by the lay person. Specifically, they require the provision to be read with knowledge of a relevant provision of an Act of general application, especially the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth) ('AIA'). A person who does not possess this specialist knowledge could well take a different view of the meaning of the provisions.

1. Introduction

The work presented in this document has been made in the context of Project C, “Compliance by Design (CbD) and Compliance through Design (CtD) solutions to support automated information sharing”, within the Law and Policy Program, Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre (D2D CRC).

The report examines central provisions of the spent convictions scheme in the *Crimes Act 1914* (Cth): ss 85ZV and 85ZW and associated definitions. The central provisions are set out in Appendix A.

The main purposes of the report are three-fold: first, to ascertain what interpretative issues may arise; second, to determine what *types* of interpretative issues may arise; and third, to indicate the potential causes of the issues.

In this report ‘interpretative issues’ is broadly understood as capturing readings of a provision that require interpretative knowledge beyond a literal reading. It includes the classic interpretative issue where rival contentions as to meaning — called here ‘constructions’ — may arise. Some of these ‘issues’ may be weak or tenuous. It also includes the application of the law where that application involves a value judgement and requires taking into account the context of the provision. And it includes ‘readings’ of the provision where that reading is informed by legal knowledge of a relevant provision of an Act of general application, such as the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). The application of provisions of these Acts may produce a reading that is different to what a lay person would arrive at uninformed by such knowledge.

The research method employed involved reading the legislation in context and in the light of possible scenarios. The legislation was read in the context of interpretative principles, legislative history and case law. In addition, other State and Territory legislation was located and compared with the Commonwealth legislation. Despite these objective criteria, the method of eliciting potential interpretative issues is still somewhat speculative, in two senses. First, some of the issues may be remote or weakly raised. Second, the method cannot be guaranteed to elicit every possible scenario and every possible interpretative issue.

2. Legal Analysis: Preliminary Findings

The provisions appear to be well drafted. However, potential interpretative issues may be identified. In summary, 19 potential interpretative issues in the central provisions of the spent convictions scheme are identified in section 3 of this report. The issues are of three types. For convenience, they are labelled categories A, B and C. These categories are now briefly described.

2.1. Category A

The potential for issues in this category to arise is deliberately created. The potential is a by-product of the drafter using a style of drafting known as general principles drafting. Turnbull defines this style as:

General principles drafting is one of several names for the style used when the drafter deliberately states the law in general principles and leaves the details to be filled in by the courts, by subordinate legislation or in some other way. (Turnbull 1997: 26)

Other names for this style are ‘fuzzy law’ and ‘conceptual specification’:

Fuzzy law, on the other hand, provides general principles in the context of broad legislative purposes (Campbell 1996: [1])

With conceptual specification a desired element or outcome is described in a broad way with its meaning and application to particular facts left to be worked out on a case by case basis. (Logan 2016)

The *Plain English Manual* of the Office of Parliamentary Counsel (Cth) states that the general principles style ‘has a big disadvantage: the precise meaning is uncertain’: [15]. With great respect, this is apt to mislead. What the Manual must be taken to mean is: it is not possible to be certain about each and every circumstance that potentially falls within a term expressed in general principles. But a term expressed in general principles will be clear in its application most of the time. This is orthodox legal and linguistic understanding. For law, see Bennion 1990: 239:

... it is unlikely the application of a statutory term will be doubtful in *every* case ... what we are in practice concerned with is the broad term whose application *to some cases* is clear and to others doubtful (first emphasis in original; second emphasis added).

Consistent with Bennion is the linguist, Sanford Schane. On the broad term ‘manufactured’, he writes:

Now, if we were to set up a scale labelled *unmanufactured* at the left end and *manufactured* at the right end, we would have no difficulty in placing the chicken and the lettuce at the very left end of this scale and in situating the computer and the desk at the very right end. But in between these two clear end points there extends an intermediate area, where there is no longer complete certainty and where vagueness enters. (Schane 2006: 23)

Instances in the sample of issues knowingly created by the drafter are issues (1)-(4) in section 3 of the report below.

2.2. Category B

The potential for issues in this category to occur arises for reasons other than due to the deliberate use of broad legislative terms. Potential sources of doubt as to the meaning of legislative provisions are numerous and diverse: Barnes 2008:

148. Bennion cites 5 ‘doubt-factors’ linked to the drafter: 1990: chs 15-19. Twining and Miers list 36 potential conditions of doubt: Twining and Miers 2010: ch 6. Barnes illustrates at length, for legislation, the Twining and Miers model: Barnes 2008: 126-47. Although the threat that sources of doubt raise may be minimised, they are ineradicable: Barnes 2008: 148-9; Bennion 1990: 213.

Instances in the sample are issues (5)-(12) in section 3 of the report below. Issue 12 seems probable. But it could be argued that other interpretative ‘issues’ identified are unlikely or less likely to arise or, if they arise, the arguments for one side may be weak. In other words, the ‘issue’ may be tenuous. In some cases I have been able to show how the interpretative context would eliminate or minimise such potential issues.

2.3. Category C

The potential for issues in this category arises because of a potential difference of views amongst interpreters: Twining and Miers 2010: 182. The provisions concerned are not ambiguous to the well-informed interpreter, but they require that person to apply specialist interpretative knowledge not ordinarily possessed by the lay person. Specifically, they require the provision to be read with knowledge of a relevant provision of an Act of general application, especially the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth) (‘AIA’). Others include the *Defence Act 1903* (Cth) and the *Ministers of State Act 1952* (Cth).

The AIA is used to shorten Acts. When a provision of the AIA is attracted to a statutory provision in question by reason that it is relevant to the provision, it prima facie amplifies that provision. Unless there is a contrary intention in the provision in question, the provision is read with the relevant provision of the AIA. Quite often the application of a provision of the AIA gives the provision a different scope to what it would otherwise be given. Consequently, a person who does not possess this specialist knowledge could well take a different view of the meaning of the provisions.

Instances are issues (13)-(19) in section 3 of the report below.

3. Legal Analysis: Potential Interpretative Issues

3.1 A. Potential for Interpretative Issues Deliberately Created

(1) Section 85ZL(b) — ‘Commonwealth law’ — ‘instrument’

For the meaning of ‘Commonwealth offence’ in s 85ZV, we go to the definition in s 85ZL. This defines it in terms of a ‘Commonwealth law’. And this concept is defined separately in s 85ZL as:

Commonwealth law means:

- (a) an Act other than:

- (i) the *Australian Capital Territory (Self-Government) Act 1988*; or
- (ii) the *Northern Territory (Self-Government) Act 1978*;
- (b) **an instrument** (including rules, regulations or by-laws) made under an Act (other than an Act referred to in subparagraph (a)(i) or (ii)); or
- (c) any other legislation that applies as a law of the Commonwealth (other than legislation in so far as it is applied by an Act referred to in subparagraph (a)(i) or (ii)), to the extent that it operates as such a law.

What is the scope of ‘an instrument’? ‘Instrument’ is a general word that is not here exhaustively defined (see ‘including’). A preliminary matter is: does ‘an instrument’ include a non-legislative instrument (the wider construction) or does it cover only a legislative instrument (the narrow construction? If the word is read in isolation and literally, the answer is yes. It is to be noted that the term ‘legislative instrument’ is not used. But the term being defined, ‘Commonwealth law’, and the content of the paragraphs (a) and (c) suggest otherwise, as do the examples in parentheses: ‘(including rules, regulations or by-laws)’. They are all of a legislative character. So the argument for the wider construction appears weak if not untenable. However, it should be noted that the finding, that ‘instrument’ means an instrument of a legislative character, is an interpretation arrived at by reading the term contextually.

A further interpretative issue arises with respect to the scope of ‘an instrument’ in the sense of (as concluded above) an instrument of a legislative character. The drafter has clearly employed general principles drafting in choosing the word ‘instrument’ and the inclusive word ‘including’. A judgment will need to be made on a case-by-case basis as to whether an instrument, that is not described as a rule, regulation or by-law, partakes of a legislative character.

(2) Section 85ZW(a) — scope of ‘or otherwise’

Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law, or any State law or Territory law, where, under section 85ZV, it is lawful for a person not to disclose, in particular circumstances, or for a particular purpose, the fact that he or she was charged with, or convicted of, an offence:

- (a) it is lawful for the person to claim, in those circumstances, or for that purpose, on oath **or otherwise**, that he or she was not charged with, or convicted of, the offence; and

The meaning of ‘or otherwise’ in paragraph (a) is potentially ambiguous. Its meaning is coloured by the words ‘on oath’. Does ‘or otherwise’ mean ‘by any means other than on oath’ (the wide, literal construction)? Or do the words mean ‘by other means that are like an oath’ (the narrow construction, influenced by the noscitur a sociis presumption of statutory interpretation)? In answering that question, regard would be had to the purpose of the provision and to any relevant extrinsic materials including case law.

If the latter construction is the better view, then a judgment will need to be made on a case-by-case basis.

(3) Section 85ZW(b) — scope of ‘anyone else who ... could reasonably be expected to know’

Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law, or any State law or Territory law, where, under section 85ZV, it is lawful for a person not to disclose, in particular circumstances, or for a particular purpose, the fact that he or she was charged with, or convicted of, an offence:

- (a) it is lawful for the person to claim, in those circumstances, or for that purpose, on oath or otherwise, that he or she was not charged with, or convicted of, the offence; and
- (b) **anyone else who** knows, or **could reasonably be expected to know**, that section 85ZV applies to the person in relation to the offence shall not:

The scope of ‘anyone else who ... could **reasonably** be expected to know’ requires a value judgment after taking account of the statutory context and the circumstances in question. Different decision-makers will inevitably at times make different judgments as to who could reasonably be expected to know. But this does not mean its application will always or even often be contestable.

(4) Section 85ZV(3)(c) — ‘a law dealing with the disclosure or taking into account of spent convictions’

(3) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any Territory law, where:

- (a) a person was convicted of a State offence;
- (b) subsection (2) does not apply to the person in relation to the offence; and
- (c) under a law in force in that State, being **a law dealing with the disclosure or taking into account of spent convictions** (however described in that law)

The drafter has used the general principles style of drafting to refer to relevant State laws. The reference to ‘however described in that law’ makes clear that it is the substance of the State law rather than its form with which the Commonwealth section is concerned. Because of that style of drafting, a judgment will have to be made as to whether a State law, though not in terms a law dealing with the disclosure or taking into account of spent convictions, is caught by s 85ZV(3)(c). However, given the current form of comparable State law (see Appendix B), this issue may not arise.

3.2 B. Potential Interpretative Issues Not Deliberately Created

(5) Section 85ZM(1) — scope of definition of ‘convicted of an offence’

85ZM Meaning of *conviction* and *spent conviction*

- (1) For the purposes of this Part, a person shall be taken to have been convicted of an offence if:
- (a) the person has been convicted, whether summarily or on indictment, of the offence;
 - (b) the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged without conviction; or
 - (c) the person has not been found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence.

What of facts such as where a person *has* been convicted but a conviction has not been recorded? Or where a person pleaded guilty but later revoked that plea? A possible interpretative issue is: is s 85ZM(1) a comprehensive (exhaustive) definition, or is it an enlarging definition but not a comprehensive definition? A comprehensive definition ‘sets out to provide a full statement of everything that is to be taken as included in the term’: Bennion 2009: 62. An enlarging definition ‘is designed to make clear that the term includes a meaning that otherwise would or might be taken as lying outside it’: Bennion 2009: 61.

An indication that the definition is not comprehensive is the omission of the words ‘if and only if’ or the word ‘means’ in the chapeau. In other words, alternative words could have been provided if it had been the purpose to provide a comprehensive definition. Further, the words ‘shall be taken to have been convicted’ is deeming language, indicative of an enlarging purpose. They do not in themselves indicate a purpose of being comprehensive.

On the other hand, indications that the definition is comprehensive and not merely enlarging are:

- Paragraph (a) includes the standard instance of ‘convicted’. If the section was intended to be merely enlarging and not comprehensive, there would have been no need for paragraph (a).
- The level of detail in the definition.

Overall, at this stage, it would appear that the arguments for the wider construction (merely enlarging) appear weak.

(6) Section 85ZM(1)(b) — Meaning of ‘convicted of an offence’ — ‘without conviction’

- (1) For the purposes of this Part, a person shall be taken to have been convicted of an offence if:

...

- (b) the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged **without conviction**; or

The section raises a possible interpretative issue as to what is the scope of 'without conviction'. Does it, for instance, encompass a conviction *not recorded*? State law may refer to a person who has been guilty but for which a conviction is *not recorded*. For example, the *Sentencing Act* 1991 (Vic) s 8:

- (2) Except as otherwise provided by this or any other Act, a finding of guilt without the recording of a conviction must not be taken to be a conviction for any purpose.

Compare the Commonwealth law which catches a person who has been 'discharged without conviction'.

(7) Section 85ZM(2)(a) — definition of 'spent conviction'

- (2) For the purposes of this Part, a person's conviction of an offence is spent if:
 - (a) the person has been granted a pardon for **a reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence**; or

The provision requires a judgment of what is a 'reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence'. Note that a judgment will have to be made about the reason.

(8) Section 85ZV(1) — meaning of 'any other Commonwealth law' — scope of later Commonwealth laws

- (1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law,

There is a potential interpretative question arising from the reference to 'any other Commonwealth law'.

A preliminary matter is: does this phrase mean any other Commonwealth law enacted *prior to* s 85ZV (the narrow construction), or does it include any other Commonwealth law, including laws enacted *after* the enactment of s 85ZV (the wider construction)? Literally, it means any other Commonwealth law including laws enacted after the enactment of s 85ZV (an Act is presumed to be 'always speaking'). However, the Crimes Act is an ordinary Act. It cannot control or determine the meaning of future Commonwealth Acts. Thus, constitutionally, it is clear that the scope of the provision refers to any other Commonwealth law enacted *before* s 85ZV. Therefore, this preliminary matter does not raise a viable alternative construction.

However, an interpretative issue can still arise with respect to the scope of *later Commonwealth laws*. If express words in such a law are used to override s 85ZV there will be no difficulty in reading the scope of the later law and s 85ZV. But if express words are not used in a later law to refer to s 85ZV, an issue may arise: was it the intention of the Parliament that passed the later law to qualify s 85ZV?

(9) Section 85ZV(1) — potential judgment about a State law or Territory law which conflicts with Part VIIC

- (1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or **any State law or Territory law**,

This may require interpretation of Part VIIC and a State or Territory law to determine whether a State law or Territory law conflicts with Part VIIC.

(10) Section 85ZV(1) — ‘is not required’

85ZV Spent convictions

- (1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, if a person’s conviction of a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence is spent, the person **is not required**:

- (a) in any State or Territory—to disclose to any person, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or
- (b) in a foreign country—to disclose to any Commonwealth authority or State authority in that country, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence.

Assume a person who could have relied on the provision does not do so. The disclosure is made. But then the person changes his or her mind. Can the person *revoke* the disclosure? This is an issue as to an implication.

(11) Section 85ZV(1)(a)— meaning of ‘disclose’

- (1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, if a person’s conviction of a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence is spent, the person is not required:

- (a) in any State or Territory—to **disclose** to any person, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or

The word ‘disclose’ has a number of dictionary meanings (Macquarie Dictionary Online; Oxford English Dictionary). Does ‘disclose’ have the narrow meaning of ‘reveal [something that is previously hidden]’, or does it have the wider meaning of ‘make known’? It is likely that the wider construction is the intended meaning.

(12) Section 85ZV(1)(a) and (b) read with s 85ZM(1) — ‘the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence’

85ZM Meaning of *conviction* and *spent conviction*

- (1) For the purposes of this Part, a person shall be taken to have been convicted of an offence if:

- (a) the person has been convicted, whether summarily or on indictment, of the offence;

- (b) the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged without conviction; or
- (c) the person has not been found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence.

...

85ZV Spent convictions

(1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, if a person's conviction of a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence is spent, the person is not required:

- (a) in any State or Territory—to disclose to any person, for any purpose, **the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence**; or
- (b) in a foreign country—to disclose to any Commonwealth authority or State authority in that country, for any purpose, **the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence**.

The charge and the conviction are the key facts to which the release from the requirement to disclose applies. It may be observed that a host of facts pertain to a person's criminal history apart from the charge and conviction itself, including:

- appearances in a court
- a plea of guilty
- sentencing decision.

The potential interpretative issue which arises is: are facts incidental or relating to a charge or conviction (especially facts that have led up to a charge or conviction), caught? One construction of the phrase is: only a charge and conviction are caught (the narrow construction).

On the other hand, a wider construction is: facts incidental or relating to a charge or conviction (especially facts that have led up to a charge or conviction) are also caught.

An indication for the narrow construction is the drafting style employed in the provisions concerned. It is the traditional, detailed style: Turnbull 1997. This is evident not only in the particulars given ('charged'; 'convicted') but also in the provision deeming a person to be 'convicted' in the circumstances set out in s 85ZM(1). This latter provision, it is to be noted, includes a finding of guilt (s 87ZM(1)(b)) and a sentence when the person is found *not* guilty: s 87ZM(1)(c). If legislation is written in 'precise language', this leaves little room for 'liberality of construction': *Victims Compensation Fund Corporation v Brown* (2003) 201 ALR 260, 269 [33]; [2003] HCA 54 (Heydon J).

Another indication of the narrow construction is the wider context of other spent convictions legislation (see Appendix B). In the case of the Australian Capital

Territory, New South Wales, the Northern Territory, South Australia and Western Australia, each uses a general principles style of drafting to cover facts which a person is not required to disclose. In the case of Victoria, it adds other specific facts using the traditional, detailed style of drafting. In summary:

- Australian Capital Territory catches:
 - ‘information about the spent conviction’: *Spent Convictions Act 2000* (ACT) s 16
 - ‘a question about the person’s criminal history’: *Spent Convictions Act 2000* (ACT) s 16
- New South Wales uses:
 - ‘information concerning the spent conviction’: *Criminal Records Act 1991* (NSW) s 12(a)
 - ‘a question concerning the person’s criminal history’: *Criminal Records Act 1991* (NSW) s 12(b)
- The Northern Territory uses:
 - ‘a question concerning ... criminal history or criminal record or a record of a similar kind’: *Criminal Records Act (Spent Convictions) Act* (NT) s 11(b)
- South Australia uses:
 - ‘a question about the person’s criminal history’: *Spent Convictions Act 2009* (SA) s 10(a)
 - ‘information concerning the spent conviction’: *Spent Convictions Act 2009* (SA) s 10(b)
- Victoria uses:
 - ‘the fact that he or she was convicted or found guilty of the offence’: *Sex Offenders Registration Act 2004* (Vic) s 72(2) (emphasis added)
- Western Australia includes:
 - ‘a dismissal’: *Spent Convictions Act 1988* (WA) s 12(a)
 - ‘a conviction that ... was deemed not to be a conviction’: *Spent Convictions Act 1988* (WA) s 12(ab).

These comparable Acts are interpretative aids for the Commonwealth legislation: see *New South Wales Crime Commission v Kelaita* (2008) 75 NSWLR 564, 580 [60]; [2008] NSWCA 284 (Allsop P):

[60] The material provided by the New South Wales Crime Commission after the hearing threw light on how the issue in question had been treated by Parliaments in the Federation. The statutes, though later than the Act, were of some real

assistance. In any proceeding in which the meaning of the Act falls for consideration, it would be generally helpful for the Court to be assisted by some understanding as to how cognate statutes in other States and the Commonwealth have dealt with the issue in question.

The comparable State and Territory legislation indicate that, if the Commonwealth Parliament had wished to catch facets of criminal history other than a charge and conviction, it could have used alternative words: the broader words used in the comparable legislation.

On the other hand, an indication for the wider construction is the Minister's second reading speech to the Crimes Legislation Amendment Bill 1989 (Cth), which included:

The spent convictions scheme is designed to give people a chance to live down a minor criminal conviction. Clearly it is in the best interests of society, and the person involved, that where the person has been convicted of a minor offence, has paid the penalty and subsequently been of good behaviour for an extended period then **he should be protected from those who might discriminate against him.**

(Commonwealth, *Parliamentary Debates*, House of Representatives, 11 May 1989, p 2543 (Mr Bowen); emphasis added)

Although not a conclusive indication of legislative purpose, the Minister's speech is an indication of the legislative purpose. It indicates that the purpose is to protect a person who has been charged or convicted from discrimination.

3.3 C. Interpretation Involving Presumptive Application of Relevant Provisions of Acts of General Application, especially the Acts Interpretation Act 1901 (Cth)

(13) Section 85ZL — definition of 'Commonwealth authority' — 'a Commonwealth Minister'

Commonwealth authority means:

- (a) a Commonwealth Minister;

The term 'Minister' is governed by various Acts of general application. Section 2B of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth) states that 'Minister' means 'one of the Ministers of State for the Commonwealth'. The *Ministers of State Act 1952* (Cth) indicates that a 'Minister of State' includes persons designated by the Governor-General as parliamentary secretaries:

4 Number of Ministers

The number of the Ministers of State must not exceed:

- (a) in the case of those designated, when appointed by the Governor-General, as Parliamentary Secretary—12; and

- (b) in the case of those not so designated—30.

Section 19(2) of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth) also informs us how to work out who is a Minister:

(2) Instruments including the following, as in force on the relevant day, or any earlier day, may be used to work out which Minister (or Ministers) is referred to under subsection (1):

- (a) an Administrative Arrangements Order;
- (b) a substituted reference order under section 19B.

Note: Substituted reference orders under section 19B may have effect in relation to days before the orders are made.

(14) Section 85ZL — definition of ‘Commonwealth authority’ — ‘the Defence Force’

Commonwealth authority means:

...

- (ba) the Defence Force;

The term ‘Defence Force’ is not defined in the *Acts Interpretation Act*. However, guidance as to what it means is provided by another law of general application, the *Defence Act 1903* (Cth). It provides that ‘Defence Force’ means the Australian Defence Force: s 4(1). Further, s 17 provides:

17 The Australian Defence Force

The *Australian Defence Force* (or *ADF*) consists of the following arms:

- (a) the Royal Australian Navy;
- (b) the Australian Army;
- (c) the Royal Australian Air Force.

(15) Section 85ZL — definition of ‘Commonwealth authority’ — ‘a federal court’

Commonwealth authority means:

...

- (g) a federal court;

In the Australian legal system federal jurisdiction can be given to a State court. However, the term ‘a federal court’ refers to a federal court created by the Parliament of the Commonwealth. This is the result of applying s 2B of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth):

federal court means the High Court or any court created by the Parliament.

(16) Section 85ZL — definition of ‘Commonwealth law’ — ‘an Act’

Commonwealth law means:

- (a) **an Act** other than:
 - (i) the *Australian Capital Territory (Self-Government) Act 1988*; or
 - (ii) the *Northern Territory (Self-Government) Act 1978*;
- ...
- (c) any other legislation that applies as a law of the Commonwealth (other than legislation in so far as it is applied by an Act referred to in subparagraph (a)(i) or (ii)), to the extent that it operates as such a law.

In Commonwealth legislation, the meaning of a reference to a generic ‘Act’, is governed prima facie by s 38 of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). That provision provides that, unless there is a contrary intention, the reference is to an Act passed by the Parliament of the Commonwealth. In s 85ZL, there is no contrary intention. Note that paragraph (c) has some extension to laws of other jurisdictions.

(17) Section 85ZL definition of ‘waiting period’

waiting period, in relation to an offence, means:

- (a) if the person convicted of the offence was dealt with as a minor in relation to the conviction—the period of 5 years **beginning** on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence; or
- (b) in any other case—the period of 10 years **beginning** on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence.

When does the period of 5 years and the period of 10 years start to run? This is an interpretative question. Legally speaking, the answer to this question is fairly straightforward, having regard to s 36(1) of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). Item 2 in that subsection states that (unless a contrary intention appears) a period ‘beginning on a day’ includes that day. No contrary intention appears in s 85ZL. In other words, the period starts to run from and including the day mentioned in the definition.

The interpretative aspect to the Acts Interpretation Act is underlined by the fact that the relevant provision of that Act has a different application to what would prevail under some State Interpretation Acts. Section 44(1) of the *Interpretation of Legislation Act 1984* (Vic) has the effect that, if an Act refers to a period beginning on a day, the period does not start to run until the *next* day.

(18) Section 85ZM(2)(b) — meaning of ‘30 months’

- (2) For the purposes of this Part, a person’s conviction of an offence is spent if:

- (a) the person has been granted a pardon for a reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence; or
- (b) the person was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence, or was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence for more than **30 months**, and the waiting period for the offence has ended.

The counting of ‘30 months’ is governed prima facie by s 2G of the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). Normally, the time point for the end of a monthly period is the point immediately before the start of the corresponding day in the next month. Section 2G also deals with a period that begins on a day that has no corresponding day in the ending month, so that, eg, a monthly period beginning on 31 August ends at the end of the next month (here 30 September).

(19) Section 85ZV(1)(a) — ‘disclose to any person’

85ZV Spent convictions

(1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, if a person’s conviction of a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence is spent, the person is not required:

- (a) in any State or Territory—to disclose to **any person**, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or

What is the scope of ‘any person’? Apart from an individual, who does it cover? Section 2C in the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth), a provision relating to the meaning of the word ‘person’, has the effect of presumptively including within that word a body politic or corporate as well as an individual.

The case law on ‘body politic’ provides that a State or Territory is a body politic: *Kennedy v Anti-Discrimination Commission of the Northern Territory* (2006) 92 ALD 134, 139 [2006] NTCA 9 [31]. In addition:

- a body politic may be part of another body politic: *WorkCover Authority (NSW) v Police Service (NSW)* [2000] NSWIRComm 234 [18]
- it has been held that “The expression “body politic”, as distinguished from “body corporate”, indicates to my mind a body created for some public purpose’: *Melbourne Harbour Trust Commissioners v Colonial Sugar Refining Co Ltd* (1925) 36 CLR 230, 279, cited in *WorkCover Authority (NSW) v Police Service (NSW)* [2000] NSWIRComm 234 [22].

Consistent with the above, Pearce cites cases which apply ‘body politic’ to statutory bodies and to agencies of the Crown (a tourist bureau): Pearce 2018: 144 [5.12].

4. Conclusions

The spent conviction scheme in the Crimes Act appears to be well drafted. However, no legislative scheme is immune from potential interpretative issues, and the spent convictions scheme is no exception. But it is a misconception to see the potentiality for interpretative issues as necessarily evidence of a drafting mistake or a bad thing. And the very fact that some types of interpretative issue can be readily identified on the face of the legislation means that those mapping a legislative scheme are forewarned and can be forearmed.

Category A issues are deliberately built-in through the use of general principles drafting. The fact that this drafting can be identified on the face of the legislation means that, to some extent, issues falling within this category can be anticipated. A user of a provision drafted in the general principles style can manage a level of uncertainty associated with this style. By reading the provisions in context and particularly in the light of the purpose of the provision, the reader can clarify in advance examples of its operation (either side of the line). But the examples will not be exhaustive, will not have the force of law of course, and complete certainty cannot be achieved in the abstract.

In contrast, some interpretative issues are not deliberately created. These are category B issues. On the face of the legislation, they are difficult to predict and vary in their cogency. They are difficult to predict because the likelihood of the facts arising that would create an issue is often uncertain and in some cases may be remote. And even if facts arise to generate an issue, the weight of the interpretative arguments for one construction may vary from one provision to another. An argument for one construction may be weak. In other words, the 'issue' may be tenuous. Category B issues constitute the most problematic type of issue for the administrator.

Category C issues are like and unlike Category B issues. While they are also not deliberately created, they *can* be readily identified on the face of the legislation. They comprise 'issues' created by the reliance on Acts of general application, especially the *Acts Interpretation Act 1901* (Cth). In this report no issue of contrary intention was evident and no competing constructions could be formulated so as to create a full-blown problem. The interpretative significance of the AIA and other Acts of general application is that, while a reader who is aware of the Act of general application may read the provisions in this category one way, a lay reader who is unaware of the Act of general application may read it another way. However, the fact that, as regards the present scheme, a provision of an Act of general application can be readily identified as of relevance (and for which, as mentioned, there is no issue of contrary intention in the provision in question) means that those mapping the legislative scheme can build the effect of the relevant provisions of the AIA into their design. In short, like the category A issue, but more so, the Category C issue can be readily identified on the face of the legislation and can be factored in by an analyst of legislation.

5. References

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6. Appendix A: Central Provisions in the Federal Spent Convictions Scheme

Crimes Act 1914 (Cth)

Part VIIC—Pardons, quashed convictions and spent convictions

Division 3—Spent convictions

85ZV Spent convictions

(1) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, if a person's conviction of a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence is spent, the person is not required:

- (a) in any State or Territory—to disclose to any person, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or
- (b) in a foreign country—to disclose to any Commonwealth authority or State authority in that country, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence.

(2) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any Territory law, if a person's conviction of a State offence or a foreign offence is spent, the person is not required:

- (a) in any Territory—to disclose to any person, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or
- (b) in any State or foreign country—to disclose to any Commonwealth authority in that State or country, for any purpose, the fact that the person has been charged with, or convicted of, the offence.

(3) Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law or any Territory law, where:

- (a) a person was convicted of a State offence;
- (b) subsection (2) does not apply to the person in relation to the offence; and
- (c) under a law in force in that State, being a law dealing with the disclosure or taking into account of spent convictions (however described in that law) it is lawful for the person, in particular circumstances or for a particular purpose, not to

disclose the fact that the person was charged with, or convicted of, the offence;

the person is not required, in corresponding circumstances or for a corresponding purpose:

(d) in a Territory—to disclose the fact that the person was charged with, or convicted of, the offence; or

(e) in a State or foreign country—to disclose that fact to any Commonwealth authority in that State or country.

85ZW Effect of right of non-disclosure

Subject to Division 6, but despite any other Commonwealth law, or any State law or Territory law, where, under section 85ZV, it is lawful for a person not to disclose, in particular circumstances, or for a particular purpose, the fact that he or she was charged with, or convicted of, an offence:

(a) it is lawful for the person to claim, in those circumstances, or for that purpose, on oath or otherwise, that he or she was not charged with, or convicted of, the offence; and

(b) anyone else who knows, or could reasonably be expected to know, that section 85ZV applies to the person in relation to the offence shall not:

(i) without the person's consent, disclose the fact that the person was charged with, or convicted of, the offence to any other person, or to a Commonwealth authority or State authority, where it is lawful for the first-mentioned person not to disclose it to that other person or that authority; or

(ii) in those circumstances, or for that purpose, take account of the fact that the person was charged with, or convicted of, the offence.

7. Appendix B: State and Territory Legislation Relating to Release from Requirement to Disclose Criminal History

AUSTRALIAN CAPITAL TERRITORY

SPENT CONVICTIONS ACT 2000 - SECT 16

What are the consequences of a conviction becoming spent ?

If a conviction of a person is spent —

- (a) the person is not required to disclose information about the spent conviction to anyone; and
- (b) a question about the person's criminal history is taken not to refer to the spent conviction, but to refer only to any of the person's convictions that are not spent ; and

NEW SOUTH WALES

CRIMINAL RECORDS ACT 1991 - SECT 12

What are the consequences of a conviction becoming spent ?

If a conviction of a person is spent :

- (a) the person is not required to disclose to any other person for any purpose information concerning the spent conviction, and
- (b) a question concerning the person's criminal history is taken to refer only to any convictions of the person which are not spent , and

NORTHERN TERRITORY

CRIMINAL RECORDS (SPENT CONVICTIONS) ACT - SECT 11

Person not required to disclose spent record

Subject to this Part, where a record is a spent record:

- (a) the person to whom it relates is not required to disclose to another person that spent record;
- (b) a question concerning a person's convictions, criminal history or criminal record or a record of a similar kind shall be taken to refer only to a record which is not a spent record; and
- (c) in the application to a person of a provision of an Act or instrument of a legislative or administrative character:

(i) a reference to a conviction, criminal history or criminal record or record of a similar kind shall be taken to be a reference only to a record which is not a spent record; and

(ii) a reference to a person's character or fitness shall not be taken as permitting or requiring a spent record to be taken into account.

QUEENSLAND

CRIMINAL LAW (REHABILITATION OF OFFENDERS) ACT 1986 - SECT 6

Non-disclosure of convictions upon expiration of rehabilitation period

Where the rehabilitation period has expired in relation to a conviction recorded against any person and the conviction has not been revived in respect of the person, neither that person nor any other person, if the person knows that the rehabilitation period has expired, shall disclose the conviction unless—

(a) being the person against whom the conviction is recorded—the person wishes to disclose the conviction; or

(b) the person makes the disclosure under the authority of a permit granted under *section 10* in accordance with the conditions (if any) of the permit; or

(c) the person makes the disclosure in circumstances that constitute an exception to the operation of *section 9 (1)* or that are expressed by *section 9 (2)* to be a case to which the provisions of *section 9 (1)* do not apply.

SOUTH AUSTRALIA

SPENT CONVICTIONS ACT 2009 - SECT 10

10—Ability to disregard spent convictions

If a conviction of a person is spent —

(a) a question about the person's criminal history is taken not to refer to the spent conviction, but to refer only to any of the person's convictions that are not spent ; and

(b) the person is not required to disclose to any other person for any purpose information concerning the spent conviction; and

VICTORIA

SEX OFFENDERS REGISTRATION ACT 2004 - SECT 72

Effect of spent convictions

(1) The fact that an offence in respect of which a registrable offender has been found guilty becomes spent does not affect—

(a) the status of the offence as a registrable offence for the purposes of this Act in respect of the registrable offender; or

(b) any reporting obligations of the registrable offender.

(2) For the purposes of this section, an offence becomes spent if, under a law in any jurisdiction, the registrable offender is permitted to not disclose the fact that he or she was convicted or found guilty of the offence.

WESTERN AUSTRALIA

SPENT CONVICTIONS ACT 1988 - SECT 12

12 . Application of Part 3

This Part applies to —

(a) a dismissal under —

(i) section 669(1)(a) of *The Criminal Code*²; and

(ii) section 34 or 34B of the *Child Welfare Act 1947*⁴;

and

(ab) a conviction that under section 20 of the *Offenders Community Corrections Act 1963*³ was deemed not to be a conviction; and

(ac) a conviction that under section 40(2) of the *Child Welfare Act 1947*⁴ was deemed not to be a conviction; and

(b) a charge formally made in court that a person has committed an offence where —

(i) the charge is withdrawn; or

(ii) the charge is disposed of without a conviction being recorded,

as if the dismissal or charge were a spent conviction.

SPENT CONVICTIONS ACT 1988 - SECT 15

15 . Bail decisions not affected by s. 25, 26 or 27

Sections 25(1) and (2), 26(1) and 27 do not apply for the purposes of any decision relating to the bail of a person for an appearance in a court.

SPENT CONVICTIONS ACT 1988 - SECT 27

27. Disclosure or acknowledgment of spent convictions

(1) Questions about a convicted person put to that person or any other person shall not be taken to relate to a spent conviction or the charge to which the conviction relates.

(2) A rule of common law or equity, or a provision of an agreement or arrangement, that requires the disclosure or acknowledgment of matters relating to a convicted person does not require the disclosure or acknowledgment of a spent conviction or the charge to which the conviction relates.